

Coordinating Delivery Service Providers for Greener Two-Echelon Vehicle Routing via Bilevel Optimization: Exact and Data-driven Methods

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Abstract

This paper presents a single-leader multi-follower game with two echelons in urban logistics to minimize carbon emissions. The First-Mile (FM) delivery service providers from warehouses outside the city deliver parcels to micro-hubs at city outskirts so that Last-Mile (LM) service providers with greener vehicles finalize delivery to customers. The leader assigns parcels to micro-hubs and to LMs minimizing total emissions at both echelons while each FM and LM minimizes cost and respecting time windows. The present study can be viewed as a centralized collaborative logistics approach but differs from the existing literature in its formulation of the collaborative model where the preferences of all players are jointly considered by the leader through a hierarchical game structure and applies bilevel optimization for coordinated routing. To find optimal strategies, an exact cutting-plane algorithm is developed and then compared to a scalable heuristic approach based on constraint learning. The data-driven constraint learning approach solves a single-level reformulation of the bilevel problem where followers' best responses are approximated through predictive models. To model followers' best responses to leader assignment decisions, we implement a network-oriented learning approach where we learn FM and LM predictive models that can be used with large city-sized network instances. The proposed approaches are tested on realistic problems instances from Madrid and Berlin. Our findings highlight the potential of the proposed game-theoretical model for reducing emissions in urban logistics while ensuring that stakeholders' preferences such as on-time deliveries are taken into account. Our experiments also show that the data-driven method is able to find efficient solutions in competitive time.

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Highlights

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- New collaborative delivery model for greener urban logistics.
- Bilevel optimization approach where followers represent delivery service providers.
- Exact and data-driven solution methods are developed and implemented.
- Coordinated model is shown to strike a balance between carbon emissions reduction and delivery service providers operating costs.
- Constraint learning-based approach provides a tractable solution method for optimizing city-scale operations.

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1. Introduction

This study addresses the problem of coordinating Delivery Service Providers (DSPs) to reduce the carbon footprint of urban logistics. With the advent of climate change and the need to decarbonize transportation, many cities are reconfiguring last-mile deliveries via collaborative logistics. Collaborative delivery models aim to reduce both operations costs and carbon emissions by coordinating DSPs to improve operations, such as traveling shorter routes (Allen et al., 2012). Aside collaboration, cities are also transitioning towards two-echelon (2E) logistics (Savelsbergh and Van Woensel, 2016). This trend is notable in historical city centers that are frequently congested due to a lack of capacity. In this context, 2E urban logistics aim to strike a compromise by consolidating first-mile deliveries at so-called satellite hubs or lockers located at the outskirts of the city centre. This allows last-mile DSPs to operate with greener vehicles such as electric cargo bikes or low-emissions minivans (Caggiani et al., 2021). This 2E configuration aims to ensure that larger and thus higher carbon footprint delivery vehicles avoid city centres where many parcels are typically destined. Yet, the operation of collaborative delivery models via 2E distribution networks is a challenging task since one or multiple commodities must be routed efficiently via potentially multiple DSPs and through two echelons while respecting supply and demand constraints, as well as collaborators' preferences such as customer on-time deliveries.

To transition towards more sustainable urban logistics, cities are increasingly seeking to coordinate DSPs to minimize their carbon footprint. Accordingly, new regulations are developed to provide a framework for supporting greener urban logistics by coordinating DSP operations (Fontaine et al., 2023). These new regulations may take various forms such as restricting city centres to electric delivery fleets, limiting the number of vehicles operating over time and space, requesting parcels to transit through targeted satellite hubs (Schmelzer, 2014), amongst others. This motivates a collaborative logistics model where a set of DSPs operates in a 2E distribution network under the regulation of a leader entity whose goal is to reduce network-wide carbon emissions.

In this study, we investigate the collaborative 2E-VRP from a game-theoretical perspective where multiple DSPs are coordinated by a Green

Urban Logistics Platform (GULP) representing the leader entity mentioned above. Specifically, we consider multiple cost-minimizing First-Mile (FM) and Last-Mile (LM) DSPs who co-exist in the same distribution network. These DSPs are regulated by a leader working for the city who determines through which satellite hubs should parcels transit and assigns parcels to LM DSPs to coordinate customer deliveries in the network. This approach is motivated by the need to develop greener urban logistics solutions while accounting for DSPs' business models and is supported by the [URBANE \(2024\)](#) project. From a methodological standpoint, this study combines different modeling and optimization methods. We formulate this collaborative 2E-VRP model using a game-theoretical approach based on bilevel optimization ([Aussel and Svensson, 2020](#)). A hierarchical game with follower players representing DSPs and a leader player representing a GULP anticipating the best-responses of profit-maximizing DSPs is proposed.

The optimization problems of FM and LM DSPs are modeled as Vehicle Routing Problems with Time Windows (VRPTW) and Pickup-and-Delivery VRPTW (PDPTW), respectively. The leader problem is an assignment problem and the outcome of this game is an emissions-optimal leader strategy that assigns parcels to satellite hubs and to LM DSPs. To find optimal leader strategies, an exact cutting-plane algorithm is developed based on follower best-responses value function cuts. Since this approach may require the solution of an extensive amount of VRPTW and PDPTW, a data-driven heuristic approach based on constraint learning is developed to enhance computational scalability. We conduct extensive numerical experiments to demonstrate the benefits of the proposed coordinated delivery logistics model against its uncoordinated and its non-competitive counterparts. Our experiments also reveal that the proposed constraint learning-based heuristic improves on a greedy assignment approach and is capable of producing high-quality solutions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We examine the literature related to this study in [Section 2](#). The coordinated delivery problem addressed and its bilevel optimization formulation are presented in [Section 3](#). Optimization methods are introduced in [Section 4](#). Numerical experiments and results are presented in [Section 5](#) and the findings of this study are summarized in [Section 6](#).

2. Literature review and contributions

This study is related to multiple streams of literature which we review in the following sections: collaborative urban logistics ([Section 2.1](#)); game-

theoretical approaches for coordinated routing (Section 2.2); 2E-VRP (Section 2.3); green vehicle routing (Section 2.4); and data-driven optimization for vehicle routing (Section 2.5). We conclude this section by outlining research gaps and emphasizing our contributions in Section 2.6.

2.1. Collaborative urban logistics

Collaborative logistics refer to initiatives where logistics service providers cooperate via a mechanism with the goal of reducing their operations costs or increasing their profits (Gaujardo and Rönnqvist, 2015). Here we emphasize contributions in urban logistics and notably collaborative vehicle routing approaches for last-mile urban deliveries. In the collaborative vehicle routing problem, a set of DSPs may share resources such as request orders to improve their operations (Gansterer and Hartl, 2018b). Collaboration mechanisms rely on resources sharing and may be centralized or decentralized depending on the level of information available (Gansterer and Hartl, 2020). In centralized approaches, a single decision-maker is assumed to have enough information to coordinate the collaborative logistics system and decides the allocation of requests and costs among DSPs. While, the objective is often to reduce operations costs, some studies have considered alternative, sustainability-oriented goals (Pérez-Bernabeu et al., 2015; Montoya-Torres et al., 2016; Sanchez et al., 2016). In these studies, vehicle routing models for horizontal cooperation among DSPs are developed and their performance is compared with their non-cooperative counterpart. Although designed for collaborative logistics, the formulations involve a single decision-maker.

Decentralized collaborative logistics approaches consider instead multiple decision-makers who interact in a distribution network, possibly through auctions. Gansterer and Hartl (2018b) lists three streams of non-auction based decentralized studies: partner identification, request selection and request exchange methods. While the problems addressed therein are more strategic and tactical rather than operational, the solution of vehicle routing problems are often required to quantify marginal profits resulting from collaborative logistics decisions (Wang et al., 2014; Cuervo et al., 2016). Auction-based approaches typically consists of DSPs bidding for request bundles. The challenges of such approaches are multiple: if the incentives are not strong enough, DSPs may choose self-fulfilment or to withhold certain requests (Karels et al., 2020; Los et al., 2022). Since information sharing is limited in auction-based mechanisms, it can be difficult to encourage participation and the pooling of attractive requests. In addition, strategyproofness, or truthful bidding, can be difficult to enforce due to the combinatorial

nature of collaborative delivery auctions and solving the winner determination problem can be computationally challenging [Jacob and Buer \(2018\)](#); [Gansterer and Hartl \(2018a\)](#).

The present study can be viewed as a centralized collaborative logistics approach but differs from the existing literature in its formulation of the collaborative model where the preferences of all DSPs are jointly considered by the GULP through a hierarchical game structure.

2.2. Bilevel optimization approaches for coordinated routing

The incorporation of bilevel optimization approaches within delivery service planning and vehicle routing operations is an emerging field of research. As documented in the recent survey of [Caselli et al. \(2024\)](#), only a few bilevel optimization approaches for coordinated routing have been devoted to sustainability objectives. There are a number of papers that focus on the problem of charging and routing electric vehicles using bilevel optimization ([Subramanian et al., 2022](#); [Jia et al., 2022](#)). In [Leite et al. \(2022\)](#), the upper level of the bilevel optimization problem focuses on the allocation of charging stations, while the lower level focuses on fleet composition and routing. This problem is solved using variable neighbourhood descent with ant colony optimization. In [González et al. \(2022\)](#), the charging facility location and routing of EVs is handled in the upper level. At the lower level, an optimal power flow problem is solved. Their problem is reformulated as a Mathematical Program with Equilibrium Constraints (MPEC) and solved using a special ordered sets-type 1 (SOS1)-based approach with a strong duality constraint. [Parvasi et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Calvete et al. \(2023\)](#) both considered a bilevel school bus routing problem. In the former, the follower determines outsourcing decisions based on a given school bus route. In the latter, the follower represent student stop choice and the goal is to determine optimal bus routes while anticipating students' preferences. [Cerulli et al. \(2023\)](#) examined a bilevel optimization approach for assigning requests among a set of DSPs competing for requests. The leader is a logistics platform and multiple follower players represent DSPs that solve a profitable tour problem to decide whether to accept or not the assigned requests. Single-level reformulations are proposed and a branch-and-cut algorithm is developed to solve these reformulations.

The literature on using bilevel optimization to coordinate vehicle routing over two echelons is limited. [Marinakis and Marinaki \(2008\)](#) and [Partovi et al. \(2023\)](#) solve location-routing and location-inventory routing problems respectively. [Saffarian et al. \(2021\)](#), [Camacho-Vallejo et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Camacho-Vallejo et al. \(2023\)](#) use bilevel optimization to minimize emissions

in a multi-echelon supply chain logistics context. [Nath et al. \(2018\)](#) use a bilevel multi-objective formulation for the PRP and solve this problem using genetic algorithms. [Qiu et al. \(2020\)](#) solve a carbon pricing initiatives-based bilevel PRP using genetic and heuristic algorithms. While multiple echelons have been considered, these approaches do not coordinate deliveries throughout two-echelons, or track commodities.

The present study attempts to address this research gap by tracking commodities, i.e. parcels, throughout a two-echelon distribution network in a hierarchical game context.

2.3. Two-echelon vehicle routing problems

Two-echelon vehicle routing problems (2E-VRPs) have long been studied in the transportation and Operations Research (OR) literature since the seminal work of [Crainic et al. \(2009\)](#). In this stream of research, the focus has mainly been dedicated to modeling and solving 2E-VRPs using efficient exact and heuristic computational methods, as well as to explore variants of 2E-VRPs such as multi-commodity problems, side-constraints on satellite hubs, etc. In the 2E-VRP, the delivery of items is done first from a depot (or warehouse) to an intermediate facility (or satellite) by a set of First-Echelon (FE) vehicles, and then from the satellites to the customers by a second set of vehicles ([Perboli et al., 2011](#)). While there are many practical reasons for this 2E approach, the increasing amount of Low-Emission Zones (LEZ) or Low-Traffic Zones (LTZ) in cities ([Lurkin et al., 2021](#)) results in deliveries being consolidated outside a city, and transported to their final destinations by greener Second-Echelon (SE) vehicles such as cargo bikes or Electric Delivery Vehicles (EDVs) ([Savelsbergh and Van Woensel, 2016](#); [Crainic et al., 2021](#)). Two recent reviews on the different varieties, formulations and solutions of 2E-VRPs are by [Cuda et al. \(2015\)](#) and [Sluijk et al. \(2023\)](#). [Soysal et al. \(2015\)](#) combine two-echelon routing with the TDVRP in order to minimize either distance, time, fuel consumption, costs, or a combination of the aforementioned criteria. While [Dellaert et al. \(2021\)](#) study the Multi-Commodity 2E-VRP with time windows (MC-2E-VRPTW), they do not explicitly consider emissions.

A recent survey of models and methods for 2E-VRPs reveals that existing approaches have focused on centralized decision-making models where a single agent determine the operations at both echelons of the distribution network ([Sluijk et al., 2023](#)).

2.4. Green vehicle routing

Green vehicle routing problems have received an increasing attention in the OR and transportation communities over the past few decades (Macrina et al., 2020). In an effort to facilitate more environmentally sustainable vehicle routing, Bektaş and Laporte (2011) introduced the Pollution-Routing Problem (PRP). This is an extension of the VRP which seeks to minimize vehicle emissions as a function of the vehicles' speeds and travel times. Erdoğan and Miller-Hooks (2012) also introduced the green VRP to help with routing alternative-fuel powered vehicles to customers via refueling or recharging stations. In order to take into account the fact that traffic congestion varies with travel time, Franceschetti et al. (2013) extend the PRP to solve a Time-Dependent Pollution Routing Problem (TDPRP). The time-dependent fuel consumption is used as a proxy to estimate the equivalent amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions for a trip taken at a particular time. The emissions model used here is the Comprehensive Emissions Model (CEM) Barth et al. (2005); Barth and Boriboonsomsin (2008), and an overview of the emissions models used in transportation is given in Demir et al. (2014). Qian and Eglese (2016) also minimize emissions in VRPs with time-varying speeds and Huang et al. (2017) solve the TDVRP with path flexibility to minimize time-dependent emissions. Other authors also consider time-dependency to select paths in the road network to minimize costs and distance travelled Ben Ticha et al. (2021); Gmira et al. (2021).

Our study departs from well-studied green VRPs in several aspects: we consider a hierarchical game context where a collaborative delivery platform anticipates the decision of multiple cost-minimizing DSPs throughout a 2E distribution network. Sustainability goals are thus pursued by the platform while other stakeholders are solve more classical VRPs.

2.5. Data-driven optimization and its applications to vehicle routing

The use of Machine Learning (ML)-based techniques to assist combinatorial optimization methods is an active research area (Bengio et al., 2021). One of the main use of ML in the context of VRPs has been to develop more scalable data-driven solution methods (Accorsi et al., 2022). Fueled by the computational challenges of solving exactly VRPs, often using mixed-integer programming techniques, researchers have investigated the potential of ML to reduce the solution space (Tahir et al., 2021; Furian et al., 2021) and/or approximate complicating elements of the formulation such as energy consumption functions (Basso et al., 2021) or loading constraints (Zhang et al., 2022). Data-driven optimization methods have also been used in non-deterministic contexts, such as in stochastic and dynamic VRPs Hildebrandt

et al. (2023); Baty et al. (2024), same-day delivery problems (Chen et al., 2022) and in inventory problems (Taube and Minner, 2018). In this context, ML can be used to predict uncertain parameters and/or to learn optimal policies for enhancing computational performance. Recent works in the artificial intelligence community have also substantially contributed to developing the integration of ML-based techniques within OR problems (Vinyals et al., 2015; Dai et al., 2016; Khalil et al., 2017; Nazari et al., 2018).

Going beyond the predict-then-optimize paradigm, a stream of research has focused on the integration of predictive and prescriptive analytics with the aim to obtain better-informed solutions (Bertsimas and Kallus, 2020), including smart predict-then optimize (Elmachtoub and Grigas, 2022) and constraint learning (Fajemisin et al., 2023; Maragno et al., 2023). Such integrated approaches have been increasingly adopted by the transportation community to enhance decision-making in complex environments (Wang et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2023). Our study is relevant to this stream of research in that it proposes a novel data-driven heuristic approach based on constraint learning to predict the best responses of DSPs and enhance computational scalability.

2.6. Our contributions

In this study, we address the problem of coordinating multiple Delivery Service Providers (DSPs) in a multi-commodity two-echelon (2E) urban distribution network. We propose a game-theoretical approach where first- and last-mile DSPs are modeled as cost-minimizing players. A Green Urban Logistics Platform (GULP) with the goal of minimizing emissions aims to coordinate DSPs throughout the 2E network to minimize network-wide carbon emissions. From a modeling standpoint, the context of this problem is similar to that of Dellaert et al. (2021) in that we both consider a two-echelon, multi-commodity approach, and track parcels from depots to delivery nodes. We however consider the preferences of multiple decision-makers via a hierarchical game model and have capacitated satellite hubs. In both echelons, we have multiple First-Mile (FM) and Last-Mile (LM) delivery players. While these players act selfishly to optimize their own goals (i.e. minimization of travel costs and on-time deliveries), our bilevel formulation allows the leader to optimally assign parcels from the FM DSPs to the satellites, and from the satellites to the LM DSPs in such a way as to minimize the total emissions of all vehicles. We also consider two types of vehicles: internal combustion vehicle emissions for the first echelon, and electric vehicle emissions for the second echelon. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first problem of its kind in the literature. From an optimization

standpoint, we develop an exact cutting-plane approach that is based on the high-point relaxation of the bilevel optimization formulation. We also propose a more scalable data-driven heuristic approach based on the approximation of followers' best response via a constraint learning approach which is shown to be competitive.

The focus of this study is not to advance the state-of-the art in terms of VRPs algorithms. As discussed in our review of literature, there are many studies on exact and heuristic algorithms for VRPs that can be leveraged to enhance the computational performance of the VRP sub-problems that arise within the proposed approaches. Hence, in our numerical VRP sub-problems are solved using off-the-shelf Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP) solvers. Although there exists more advanced, yet generic VRP solvers (Pessoa et al., 2020; Wouda et al., 2024), these cannot accommodate pickup-and-delivery problems. Further, since satellite hub assignment decisions are optimized, hence, the pickup location of parcels in the second echelon is variable in our formulation which differs from most existing 2E-VRP formulations in the literature.

In summary, this study makes the following main contributions:

- We introduce a new game-theoretical collaborative delivery model for greener two-echelon urban logistics. We consider multiple FM and LM DSPs that coexist in a satellite hub-capacitated distribution network.
- To coordinate FM and LM DSPs, we propose a bilevel optimization formulation where followers represent cost-minimizing DSPs and the leader represents a GULP that aims to minimize carbon emissions. The assignment of parcels to satellite hubs and to LM DSPs are decision variables of the leader. FM DSPs solve a parameterized VRPTW and LM DSPs solve a parameterized PDPTW.
- We develop exact and data-driven solution methods to solve this bilevel optimization problem. The proposed constraint learning-based approach is shown to be efficient in finding high quality solutions in competitive time.
- We conduct extensive numerical experiments which demonstrate that the coordinated model is able to strike a balance between carbon emissions reduction and delivery service providers operating costs.

Figure 1: Illustration of the 2E vehicle routing problem with non-cooperative agents: two FM and two LM followers are represented and serve six parcels through three satellite hubs.

3. Problem description and formulation

We present an innovative approach that aims to capture the trade-offs between city-level stakeholders and DSPs. We consider that city-level stakeholders seek to minimize emissions while service providers seek to minimize operating costs and to maximize customer satisfaction through on-time deliveries. As this requires the coordination of several non-cooperative agents, we propose to handle them using bilevel optimization. An illustration of our approach is given in Figure 1. We formulate a Single-Leader Multi-Follower Game (SLMFG) (Aussel and Svensson, 2020), with two types of followers, first- and last-mile DSPs, such that the leader represents a collaborative GULP that seeks to minimize city-wide emissions.

3.1. Modeling approach

In this game-theoretical formulation, the first type of follower models the FM DSPs operating in the first echelon, while the second type of follower models the LM DSPs operating in the second echelon. We use the terms first-mile and first-echelon (or last-mile and second-echelon respectively) interchangeably for the remainder of this paper. We assume that the

GULP has complete information of the 2E distribution network including FM and LM depot and satellite hubs locations and parcel depot and customer locations as well as time windows data. In this regard, the proposed approach can be viewed as a centralized collaborative logistics model with full information and full compliance from stakeholders. However, unlike existing centralized collaborative logistics approaches, our approach takes into account the preferences of DSPs which may be conflicting with the goal of reducing emissions. This aims to act as an incentive model to encourage stakeholder participation in green urban logistics initiatives. The objective of the leader (GULP) is to minimize network-wide emissions by coordinating FM and LM DSPs. The operations model of FM DSPs is represented by a VRPTW where deliveries to satellite hubs are determined by the GULP. The operations of LM DSPs are dependent on both parcel satellite hub and LM follower assignment decisions. Furthermore, we assume that LMs are inclined to meet customer time windows preferences to ensure service quality but that violations may occur since their parcel assignment is determined by the GULP. Hence, we formulate LM DSPs problem as a pickup and delivery problem with soft time windows.

Formally, we denote \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{D} the sets of FM and LM DSPs, respectively; and $D_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $D_{\mathcal{D}}$ the sets of FM and LM depots, respectively. Furthermore, we use subscript f to denote FM follower and subscript d to denote a LM follower. We denote \mathcal{P} the set of parcels, \mathcal{S} the set of satellite hubs and \mathcal{C} the set of customer nodes. The set of parcels located at the depot of FM $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is denoted \mathcal{P}_f . We denote C_s the capacity of satellite $s \in \mathcal{S}$. The variables of the leader (GULP) consists of parcel to satellite assignments and parcel to LM assignment. Parcel to satellite assignment variables are defined as:

$$\lambda_p^s \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if parcel } p \in \mathcal{P} \text{ is assigned to satellite hub } s \in \mathcal{S} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Parcel to LM assignment variables are defined as:

$$y_p^d \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if parcel } p \in \mathcal{P} \text{ is assigned to LM } d \in \mathcal{D} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

We use boldface symbols to denote vectors. Given a FM follower $f \in \mathcal{F}$, we denote $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_f$ the assignment vector of parcels $p \in \mathcal{P}_f$ to satellites hubs. Given a LM follower $d \in \mathcal{D}$, we denote \boldsymbol{y}_d the assignment vector of parcels to LM d . We denote $\text{VRPTW}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}_f)$ the $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_f$ -parameterized VRPTW

of FM follower $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and its set of optimal solutions. Similarly, we denote PDPTW(λ, \mathbf{y}_d) the (λ, \mathbf{y}_d)-parameterized PDPTW of LM follower $d \in \mathcal{D}$ and its set of optimal solutions.

We use the CEM (Barth et al., 2005; Barth and Boriboonsomsin, 2008) to model the emissions of a FM vehicle k traversing an arc (i, j) as a function of the distance d_{ij} (m) covered, the constant speed v_{ij} (m/s) at which the vehicle is moving, and the load l (kg) the vehicle is carrying. Other factors affecting the fuel consumption are the engine friction factor k_e , engine speed (rev/s) N_e , engine displacement V_e , and engine-and-vehicle-related parameters $\lambda, \gamma, \beta, \alpha$ and μ . Full details of these parameters are given in Demir et al. (2011).

$$E_{ij,f}^k = \lambda \left(k_e N_e V_e \frac{d_{ij}}{v_{ij}} + \gamma \beta d_{ij} (v_{ij})^2 + \gamma \alpha (\mu + l) d_{ij} \right) \quad (3)$$

For the LM emissions where EDVs are used, we model the emissions using the approach of Nicholas (2023). Here, the equivalent grams of CO_2 (gCO₂eq) emissions are computed based on the mean kWh consumed by each vehicle, and the carbon intensity (in gCO₂eq/kWh) of the electricity generation systems. For example, if a city produces electricity using N different sources, e.g. natural gas, wind energy, biomass, coal, etc., the emissions factor ϵ_i is the carbon intensity of each power source i measured in (gCO₂eq/kWh). The corresponding generation percentage ϕ_i is the participation of each power source in the energy mix (%). If a vehicle k traversing an arc (i, j) consumes μ_{ij} kWh, the total amount of emissions (gCO₂eq) can be calculated as

$$E_{ij,d}^k = \mu_{ij} \sum_i^N \epsilon_i \phi_i \quad (4)$$

The emission factor and energy generation percentage used to evaluate the problem instances in Section 5 are given in Tables A.5 and A.6.

We denote \mathcal{K}_f the set of vehicles of FM f and \mathcal{K}_d the set of vehicles of LM d . First echelon vehicles, nodes and arcs are denoted $\mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{V}_1$ and \mathcal{A}_1 while second echelon vehicles, nodes and arcs are denoted $\mathcal{K}_2, \mathcal{V}_2$ and \mathcal{A}_2 . We use index k to denote a vehicle and indices i and j to denote locations. Accordingly, FM followers routing and arrival time variables are denoted $x_{ij,f}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ and $t_{i,f}^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$; and LM followers routing and arrival time variables are denoted $x_{ij,d}^k \in \{0, 1\}$ and $t_{i,d}^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. A comprehensive summary of the mathematical notation is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Mathematical notation

	Symbol	Description
	\mathcal{S}	Set of satellite nodes
	\mathcal{P}	Set of parcels
	\mathcal{F}	Set of DSPs in the first echelon: ($f \in \mathcal{F}$)
	\mathcal{D}	Set of DSPs in the second echelon: ($d \in \mathcal{D}$)
	\mathcal{P}_f	Set of parcels located at the depot of first-miler f
	$D_{\mathcal{F}}$	Set of first-mile depot locations
	$D_{\mathcal{D}}$	Set of last-mile depot locations
	\mathcal{C}	Set of customer nodes
Sets	\mathcal{A}_1	Set of arcs in the first echelon: $\mathcal{A}_1 = \{(i, j) \in \{D_{\mathcal{F}}\} \cup \mathcal{S} : i \neq j\}$
	\mathcal{A}_2	Set of arcs in the second echelon: $\mathcal{A}_2 = \{(i, j) \in \{D_{\mathcal{D}}\} \cup \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{C} : i \neq j\}$
	\mathcal{V}_1	Set of nodes in the first echelon
	\mathcal{V}_2	Set of nodes in the second echelon
	\mathcal{K}_f	Set of vehicles used in the first echelon for each first-miler f : ($k \in \mathcal{K}_f$)
	$\mathcal{K}_1 = \cup_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \mathcal{K}_f$	Set of all vehicles used in the first echelon: ($k \in \mathcal{K}_1$)
	\mathcal{K}_d	Set of vehicles used in the second echelon for each DSP d : ($k \in \mathcal{K}_d$)
	$\mathcal{K}_2 = \cup_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \mathcal{K}_d$	Set of all vehicles used in the second echelon
	$E_{ij,f}^k$	Emissions cost of traversing arc (i, j) by first-mile vehicle k
	$E_{ij,d}^k$	Emissions cost of traversing arc (i, j) by last-mile vehicle k
	C_s	Capacity at a satellite s
	c_{ij}	Cost of traversing arc (i, j)
	e_i	Earliest delivery time at node i
Parameters	l_i	Latest delivery time at node i
	π^E, π^L	Penalties for violating early and late customer time windows respectively
	T_{ij}	Travel time from i to j
	$M_{ij} \geq l_j + T_{ij}$	Big-M value for each arc (i, j)
	N_p^k	Big-N value for parcel p carried on vehicle k
	ρ_S, ρ_D	Design penalties on the number of satellite hubs and last-mile DSPs
	$x_{ij,f}^k \in \{0, 1\}$	Denotes if first-mile vehicle k traverses arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}_1$
	$x_{ij,d}^k \in \{0, 1\}$	Denotes if last-mile vehicle k traverses arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}_2$
	$\lambda_p^s \in \{0, 1\}$	Denotes if parcel p is delivered to satellite s
Variables	$y_p^d \in \{0, 1\}$	Denotes if parcel p is assigned to DSP d
	$t_{i,f}^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Arrival time of first-mile vehicle k at node $i \in \mathcal{V}_1$
	$t_{i,d}^k \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Arrival time of last-mile vehicle k at node $i \in \mathcal{V}_2$
	$\alpha_{ki}^E \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Early time window violation time of last-mile vehicle k at node $i \in \mathcal{V}_2$
	$\alpha_{ki}^L \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Late time window violation time of last-mile vehicle k at node $i \in \mathcal{V}_2$
	$\gamma_S, \gamma_D \in \mathbb{Z}^+$	Number of satellite hubs and LM DSPs in the single-level reformulation (14)

3.2. Leader problem

The leader decides both the assignments of parcels to satellites, as well as the proposition of parcels to LMs. All FMs must deliver all parcels to their assigned satellites, while LMs pickup from satellites and deliver to customers. Each satellite has a finite capacity and can be visited more than once, however all delivery nodes must be visited only once.

$$\min_{\lambda, \mathbf{y}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_1} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_1} E_{ij,f}^k x_{ij,f}^k + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2} E_{ij,d}^k x_{ij,d}^k \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_f} \lambda_p^s \leq C_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (5b)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_p^s = 1 \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \quad (5c)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} y_p^d = 1 \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \quad (5d)$$

$$G(\lambda, \mathbf{y}) \geq 0 \quad (5e)$$

$$\lambda_p^s \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (5f)$$

$$y_p^d \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (5g)$$

$$(\mathbf{x}_f, \mathbf{t}_f) \in \text{VRPTW}(\lambda_f) \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \quad (5h)$$

$$(\mathbf{x}_d, \mathbf{t}_d) \in \text{PDPTW}(\lambda, \mathbf{y}_d) \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (5i)$$

The leader's objective function (5a) seeks to minimize the total emissions in both echelons. Constraint (5b) respects the capacity of the satellites while assigning parcels to them, while constraint (5c) ensures that a parcel is only assigned to one satellite. Once a parcel has been assigned to a satellite, it must be picked up for delivery to its final destination. Constraint (5d) ensures that each parcel is picked up by only one LM DSP. Constraint (5e) represents a set of generic integer-linear side-constraints that could be included to guide the optimization towards certain platform designs such as minimal service constraints for satellite hubs and/or LM DSPs. Each FM follower f solves a VRPTW while dropping off parcels at the satellites (5h), while in (5i), each LM follower d solves a PDPTW (Dumas et al., 1991) based on the parcels assigned to it by the leader.

We adopt an optimistic bilevel formulation approach (Aussel and Svensson, 2020) in which, in case of multiple follower best responses, the leader is assumed to be able to select the most favourable outcome with regards to its own goal.

3.3. First-mile follower problem

The model for a FM follower f is given as

$$\text{VRPTW}(\lambda_f) : \min_{\mathbf{x}_f, \mathbf{t}_f} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_f} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_1} c_{ij} x_{ij,f}^k \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_1} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_f} x_{is,f}^k \geq \lambda_p^s \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_f, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (6b)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} x_{D_f s, f}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f \quad (6c)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_1} x_{ij, f}^k - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_1} x_{ji, f}^k = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f, j \in \mathcal{V}_1 \quad (6d)$$

$$t_{i, f}^k + T_{ij} \leq t_{j, f}^k + (1 - x_{ij, f}^k) M_{ij} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f, (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}_1 \quad (6e)$$

$$e_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_1} x_{ij, f}^k \leq t_{i, f}^k \leq l_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_1} x_{ij, f}^k \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f, i \in \mathcal{V}_1 \quad (6f)$$

$$x_{ij, f}^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f, (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}_1 \quad (6g)$$

$$t_{i, f}^k \geq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_f, i \in \mathcal{V}_1. \quad (6h)$$

The FM follower's objective function (6a) is to minimize the total route cost associated with delivering its set of parcels \mathcal{P}_f . Constraint (6b) ensures that for each parcel assigned to that first-miler, if a parcel p is assigned to a satellite s , the first-mile vehicle k travels to that satellite. Constraint (6c) states that a first-miler may leave its depot D_f and travel to a satellite s . Constraints (6d) and (6e) model flow conservation and arrival times in the first-echelon respectively, while (6f) ensures that arrival at a node i occurs within the node's time windows. The vehicles used in this echelon are large trucks with conventional internal combustion engines, and are assumed to have ample capacity. First-mile operations must take place before the last-mile followers begin operations, and this precedence is enforced via the available travel time periods in the problem data.

3.4. Last-mile follower problem

In the second echelon, the vehicles used are EDVs, and their capacities and ranges are assumed to be sufficient such that recharging or multiple trips are not required. On-time deliveries to customer is critical to ensure a quality of service. While LM followers seek to meet customer time windows, the GULP is concerned with emissions reductions. To capture these possibly conflicting preferences in the game-theoretical formulation, we formulate LM followers' problem as a pickup and delivery problem with soft time windows. Let π^L and π^E be the penalties incurred for late and early time window violations, respectively. In our numerical experiments, we set these penalties to large enough values such that priority is given to quality of service, i.e. on-time deliveries, compared to routing costs. This aims to ensure that LM followers solve a PDPTW while allowing the possibility of violating TW if certain leader assignment decisions cannot be perfectly accommodated from a customer TW standpoint. The model for a LM follower d is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PDPTW}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{y}_d) : \min_{\mathbf{x}_d, \mathbf{t}_d} & \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2} c_{ij} x_{ij,d}^k \\ & + \pi^L \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \max\{t_{i,d}^k - l_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ij,d}^k, 0\} \\ & + \pi^E \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \max\{e_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ij,d}^k - t_{i,d}^k, 0\} \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{j\delta(p),d}^k = y_p^d \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (7b)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} \lambda_p^s x_{sj,d}^k \geq y_p^d \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (7c)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} x_{D_d s,d}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (7d)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{sj,d}^k \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (7e)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ij,d}^k - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ji,d}^k = 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, j \in \mathcal{V}_2 \quad (7f)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_p^s (t_{s,d}^k + T_{s\delta(p)}) \leq t_{\delta(p),d}^k + (1 - y_p^d) N_p^k \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (7g)$$

$$t_{i,d}^k + x_{ij,d}^k T_{ij} \leq t_{j,d}^k + (1 - x_{ij,d}^k) M_{ij} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, (i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2 \quad (7h)$$

$$x_{ij,d}^k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}_2 \quad (7i)$$

$$t_{i,d}^k \geq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, i \in \mathcal{V}_2 \quad (7j)$$

In the objective function (7a), the last-mile follower d seeks to minimize the total routing cost, as well as the time window violations. Constraint (7b) states that if d is assigned a parcel p , it should be carried on only one of its vehicles, and the selected vehicle should go to the destination $\delta(p) \in \mathcal{V}_2$. Constraint (7c) states that if d is assigned a parcel p , the parcel should be picked up from the satellite s it was placed at during first-mile operations, while (7d) enables a vehicle to go from the depot of d to satellite s . Constraint (7e) states that a vehicle may go from a satellite to another node, while (7f) ensures flow conservation at all nodes. If a parcel is assigned to last-mile follower d , constraint (7g) models the travel time between the pickup location s and the destination $\delta(p)$. Constraint (7h) models the travel time of an arc (i, j) in the second-echelon.

By introducing variables α_{ki}^E and α_{ki}^L to model the violations of the early and late time windows respectively, and adding constraints (8b) to (8e), we can rewrite (7) as

$$\text{PDPTW}'(\lambda, \mathbf{y}_d) : \min_{\mathbf{x}_d, \mathbf{t}_d} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2} c_{ij} x_{ij,d}^k + \pi^E \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \alpha_{ki}^E + \pi^L \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \alpha_{ki}^L \quad (8a)$$

s.t. (7b) – (7j)

$$\alpha_{ki}^E \geq e_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ij,d}^k - t_{i,d}^k \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_2, k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (8b)$$

$$\alpha_{ki}^L \geq t_{i,d}^k - l_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{V}_2} x_{ij,d}^k \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_2, k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (8c)$$

$$\alpha_{ki}^E \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_2, k \in \mathcal{K}_d \quad (8d)$$

$$\alpha_{ki}^L \geq 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_2, k \in \mathcal{K}_d. \quad (8e)$$

4. Solution methods

We present two approaches for solving the bilevel optimization problem (5). In Section 4.1, we present an exact approach which uses a cutting-plane algorithm, while in Section 4.2, we propose a heuristic data-driven approach which allows us to enhance computational scalability.

4.1. Exact approach

We begin by solving the High-Point Relaxation (HPR) (9), where the leader's objective function is minimized over all leader and follower constraints.

$$\min_{\lambda, \mathbf{y}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_1} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_1} E_{ij,f}^k x_{ij,f}^k + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_2} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2} E_{ij,d}^k x_{ij,d}^k \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_f} \lambda_p^s \leq C_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (9b)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} y_p^d = 1 \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \quad (9c)$$

$$(6b) - (6h) \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \quad (9d)$$

$$(7b) - (7j), (8b) - (8e) \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (9e)$$

$$\lambda_p^s \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (9f)$$

$$y_p^d \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (9g)$$

The HPR relaxes the optimality conditions of the lower level problems, so that solving the HPR provides a lower bound (LB) on the optimal objective value of the bilevel problem (5). It can be seen that including (7g) in the HPR results in a constraint with bilinear terms. Replacing the product $\lambda_p^s t_{s,d}^k$ by θ_{ps}^k and adding constraints (10a) - (10d) allows us to reformulate the HPR as a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem.

$$\theta_{ps}^k \leq \lambda_p^s M \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (10a)$$

$$\theta_{ps}^k \geq 0 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (10b)$$

$$\theta_{ps}^k \leq t_{s,d}^k \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (10c)$$

$$\theta_{ps}^k \geq t_{s,d}^k - (1 - \lambda_p^s) M \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_d, p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (10d)$$

At each iteration n , we solve the HPR to obtain a LB, the candidate solution $(\lambda^n, \mathbf{y}^n)$ and estimates of followers' Objective Function Values (OFV)

\hat{V}_f^n, \hat{V}_d^n . We then solve the $(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^n, \mathbf{y}^n)$ -parameterized follower problems to obtain the best-response OFVs V_f^n, V_d^n . An Upper Bound (UB) on problem (5) is computed by evaluating (9a) given the values of $x_{ij,f}^{k,n}$ and $x_{ij,d}^{k,n}$ from the parameterized follower problems. If the difference between a follower's estimated OFV and its best-response OFV is greater than a value $\epsilon > 0$, we generate an optimality cut for that follower. The optimality cut corresponding to FM follower f at iteration n is

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_f} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_1} c_{ij} x_{ij,f}^k \leq V_f^n + \left(\sum_{p_f: \lambda_{p_f}^{s,n}=1} (\lambda_{p_f}^{s,n} - \lambda_{p_f}^s) + \sum_{p_f: \lambda_{p_f}^{s,n}=0} (\lambda_{p_f}^s - \lambda_{p_f}^{s,n}) \right) M_f \quad (11)$$

where M_f can be determined by solving a surrogate FM problem where f has to deliver one parcel to each satellite subject to satellite time windows constraints. Similarly, the optimality cut corresponding to LM follower d at iteration n is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}_2} c_{ij} x_{ij,d}^k + \pi^E \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \alpha_{ki}^E + \pi^L \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_d} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_2} \alpha_{ki}^L \\ \leq V_d^n + \left(\sum_{p: y_p^{d,n}=1} (y_p^{d,n} - y_p^d) + \sum_{p: y_p^{d,n}=0} (y_p^d - y_p^{d,n}) \right) M_d \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where M_d can be determined by solving a surrogate LM problem where LM d has to pickup and deliver all parcels, where at least one parcel is assigned to each satellite, subject to satellite and destination time window constraints. At each iteration, we also add an interdiction cut of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} (\lambda_p^s (1 - \lambda_p^{s,n}) + (1 - \lambda_p^s) \lambda_p^{s,n}) \\ + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} (y_p^d (1 - y_p^{d,n}) + (1 - y_p^d) y_p^{d,n}) \geq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

which prevents previously seen solutions from being repeated. The exact cutting-plane algorithm continues until the LB and UB converge, or if no optimality cuts are added. The optimal values $(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)$ can then be used by the followers to finalize their routes. This procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Exact cutting-plane approach

Data: Instance data
Result: $UB, \lambda^*, \mathbf{y}^*$
while not converged **do**
 $LB, \lambda^n, \mathbf{y}^n \leftarrow$ solve HPR (9);
 for $f \in \mathcal{F}$ **do**
 $\hat{V}_f^n \leftarrow$ solve VRPTW(λ_f^n);
 $V_f^n \leftarrow$ evaluate (6a);
 if $\hat{V}_f^n - V_f^n > \epsilon$ **then**
 | Generate optimality cut (11) for f
 end
 end
 for $d \in \mathcal{D}$ **do**
 $\hat{V}_d^n \leftarrow$ solve PDPTW($\lambda^n, \mathbf{y}_d^n$);
 $V_d^n \leftarrow$ evaluate (8a);
 if $\hat{V}_d^n - V_d^n > \epsilon$ **then**
 | Generate optimality cut (12) for d
 end
 end
 $UB \leftarrow$ evaluate (9a) and update best known solution λ^*, \mathbf{y}^* ;
 if $\frac{UB - LB}{UB} > \epsilon$ **then**
 | Add interdiction cut (13)
 end
end

4.2. Constraint learning-based heuristic

In our bilevel problem, we work for the leader. The follower problems are the leader's representations of the FM and LM DSPs' operations, and precise DSP routes are not the main target output. Instead, our focus is on the leader's optimal assignments of parcels to satellite hubs (λ^*), and to LM DSPs (\mathbf{y}^*). A data-driven prediction of the FM and LM best responses may therefore be sufficient to find efficient leader decisions. We propose a data-driven surrogate optimization problem, in which we use Constraint Learning (CL) (Fajemisin et al., 2023; Maragno et al., 2023) to replace (5h) and (5i) with trained ML models, and solve a single-level reformulation of the bilevel problem. This approach is also seen in Fajemisin et al. (2020) and Dumouchelle et al. (2024), where the lower-level problems are approximated

using ML approaches.

We implement a network-oriented learning approach where we learn FM and LM predictive models that can be used for multiple instances for a given 2E routing network. Given a maximum possible number of customer nodes, satellite hubs, and FM and LM DSPs, we generate random instances and train models to learn the emissions associated with first- and last-mile routes. The procedure for generating the data used to train these predictive models is summarized in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: Training data generation procedure

Data: Maximum 2E network
 N_f : Desired size of training dataset $\forall f \in \max |\mathcal{F}|$
 N_d : Desired size of training dataset $\forall d \in \max |\mathcal{D}|$
 /*Training datasets for each follower*/
Result: $DS_f = \{(\lambda_f^1, E_f^1), \dots, (\lambda_f^{N_f}, E_f^{N_f})\} \forall f \in \mathcal{F}$
 $DS_d = \{(\lambda^1, \mathbf{y}_d^1, E_d^1), \dots, (\lambda^{N_d}, \mathbf{y}_d^{N_d}, E_d^{N_d})\} \forall d \in \mathcal{D}$

```

for  $f \in \mathcal{F}$  do
   $DS_f \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
  for  $i = 1 \dots N_f$  do
    Randomly sample  $\lambda_f^i$  vector of the 2E network model while
    respecting constraints (5b) and (5c);
    Solve VRPTW( $\lambda_f^i$ ) to obtain best response route;
    Compute emissions  $E_f^i$  associated to best response route to
    obtain target variable;
     $DS_f \leftarrow DS_f \cup (\lambda_f^i, E_f^i)$ 
  end
end
for  $d \in \mathcal{D}$  do
   $DS_d \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
  for  $i = 1 \dots N_d$  do
    Randomly sample  $(\lambda^i, \mathbf{y}_d^i)$  vector of the 2E network model
    while respecting constraints (5b), (5c) and (5d);
    Solve PDPTW( $\lambda^i, \mathbf{y}_d^i$ ) to obtain best response route;
    Compute emissions  $E_d^i$  associated to best response route to
    obtain target variable;
     $DS_d \leftarrow DS_d \cup (\lambda^i, \mathbf{y}_d^i, E_d^i)$ 
  end
end

```

Once the data has been generated, we train one predictive model per follower to learn the emissions cost as a function of the assignment variables λ and \mathbf{y} . The data-driven surrogate CL optimization problem is:

$$\min_{\lambda, \mathbf{y}, \gamma} \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} E_f + \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} E_d + \rho_S \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \gamma_s + \rho_D \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \gamma_d \quad (14a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_f} \lambda_p^s \leq C_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (14b)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \lambda_p^s = 1 \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \quad (14c)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} y_p^d = 1 \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \quad (14d)$$

$$G(\lambda, \mathbf{y}) \geq 0 \quad (14e)$$

$$E_f = \text{Pred}(\lambda_f) \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} \quad (14f)$$

$$E_d = \text{Pred}(\lambda, \mathbf{y}_d) \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (14g)$$

$$\gamma_s \geq \lambda_p^s \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (14h)$$

$$\gamma_d \geq y_p^d \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (14i)$$

$$\lambda_p^s \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (14j)$$

$$y_p^d \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}, d \in \mathcal{D} \quad (14k)$$

The constraints (14f) and (14g) are the trained predictive models which may be represented using MILP formulations (Maragno et al., 2023; Bergman et al., 2022). E_f and E_d are the total emissions for the first- and last-mile followers respectively. The variables γ_s and γ_d represent the number of satellite hubs and LM DSPs respectively, with ρ_S and ρ_D as the design penalties on these variables. Extensive numerical experiments have revealed that these design penalties are helpful to improve the solution of the surrogate CL problem. The solution to this surrogate CL problem gives us a satellite hub and parcel assignment $(\lambda^{\text{CL}}, \mathbf{y}^{\text{CL}})$. To determine a UB on the optimal OFV of the bilevel optimization problem (5), we solve the $(\lambda^{\text{CL}}, \mathbf{y}^{\text{CL}})$ -parameterized follower problems to obtain the follower routes and true emissions cost. The surrogate CL problem is a single-level MILP with significantly fewer variables and constraints than the bilevel optimization problem (5), hence this is expected to enhance computational performance.

5. Computational analysis

We conduct numerical experiments on problem instances derived from openly available data and discuss the results. The data used to generate problem instances is presented in Section 5.1. The details of the experimental configuration is described in Section 5.2. The generation of training data and the selection of the predictive model used in the data-driven approach is discussed in Section 5.3. The experimental results are reported in Section 5.4.

5.1. Problem instances

We evaluated these modelling approaches on problem data available from [Blauth et al. \(2022\)](#). We generated 24 two-echelon problem instances from two cities, Berlin and Madrid, available in the repository. The number of FM DSPs $|\mathcal{F}|$ was set to 2 for all instances while the number of LM DSPs $|\mathcal{D}|$ and satellite hubs $|\mathcal{S}|$ was set to either 2 or 3. The number of parcels to be delivered $|\mathcal{P}|$ was set to either 10, 30 or 50. An instance named “berlin_2_3_2_50” implies $|\mathcal{F}| = 2$, $|\mathcal{D}| = 3$, $|\mathcal{S}| = 2$ and $|\mathcal{P}| = 50$. After some sensitivity analysis, the parameters ρ_S and ρ_D set to 1,000 and 10,000 for the Berlin instances, and 900 and 6,000 for the Madrid instances.

5.2. Experimental setup

All experiments were run on a desktop workstation with an Intel Core i9-12900KF CPU with 64 GB RAM and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU. The exact approach was implemented using CPLEX 22.1 ([International Business Machines Corporation, 2023](#)), while the data-driven approach was implemented using Gurobi 11.0.1 ([Gurobi Optimization, LLC, 2023](#)) and `gurobi-machinelearning 1.4.0` ([Gurobi Optimization, LLC, 2024](#)). The predictive models were trained using `scikit-learn` ([Pedregosa et al., 2011](#)). All models were implemented in Python. For the exact approach, we set a total time limit of 3,600 seconds. If this time limit was reached during an iteration, the algorithm was allowed to complete this iteration before termination. The surrogate CL model (14) was solved to optimality. Each parameterized follower problem was given a time limit of 300 seconds.

5.3. Training data generation and predictive model selection

To obtain each training instance, we also solved the follower problems with a time limit of 300 seconds. The follower problems are either solved to optimality, or return a feasible solution once the time limit is up. It should be noted that all FM follower problems were solved to optimality due to the small number of nodes in the FM. The size N_f of the training set for each

Table 2: Best hyper-parameter settings for FM and LM followers

	FM followers	LM Followers
# Neurons per hidden layer	50	(10,10)
Learning rate	0.001	0.001
Activation function	ReLU	ReLU
Optimizer	Adam	Adam

FM follower f was set to 10,000 while the size N_d of each LM follower d was set to 2,000. These numbers were chosen by evaluating the coefficient of determination (R^2) values as N_f and N_d were varied from 100 to 10,000 and 100 to 4,000 per FM and LM follower respectively. The average R^2 values for $N_f = 10,000$ and $N_d = 2,000$ were 0.94 and 0.89 for the FM and LM followers respectively. The average data generation time for the FM followers was 72 minutes while that of the LM followers was 6 days. The data generation procedure can be parallelized by running Algorithm 2 for each follower at the same time.

In order to select the most appropriate predictive models, we ran a grid search over several parameters on the following models: Linear Regression, Neural Networks, Decision Trees, Gradient Boosting Trees, and Random Forests. These models were chosen as they are the models currently supported by `gurobi-machinelearning`. Neural networks were chosen to represent both FM and LM follower problems, and their best hyper-parameter settings are given in Table 2.

5.4. Experimental results

In this section, we evaluate the benefits of using bilevel optimization to coordinate deliveries. We compare our bilevel (exact and data-driven) approaches to the greedy approach used by our industrial partner within the [URBANE \(2024\)](#) project. In this greedy approach, parcels are first assigned to satellite hubs based on the proximity of the satellite hubs to the final recipients. The parcels are then assigned to LM DSPs based on the proximity of the DSPs to the satellite hubs. The FM and LM DSPs then solve (6) and (8), respectively, to obtain optimal routes. This greedy approach can be viewed as an uncoordinated heuristic model with regards to the coordinated, bilevel optimization formulation (5).

5.4.1. Value of bilevel formulation

In order to evaluate the usefulness of the bilevel formulation, we compared the total emissions and the follower objective function values when

Figure 2: Comparing modelling formulations: “madrid_2_3_2_50” instance.

using the bilevel formulation against the corresponding values in the uncoordinated (greedy) approach, as well as against its non-competitive counterpart. The non-competitive counterpart formulation corresponds to the case where followers’ preferences, i.e. objective functions, are ignored and is thus mathematically equivalent to the HPR relaxation (9).

Figures 2a and 2b respectively show the total emissions and LM follower costs for the three modelling approaches, i.e. non-competitive, bilevel and uncoordinated (greedy), for the “madrid_2_2_2_30” instance. Only the LM values are shown, as there is no appreciable change in the FM objective function values. For the sake of comparison, the values are plotted as a percentage of the bilevel values. It can be seen that the bilevel formulation strikes a balance between total emissions and follower costs. The non-competitive case gives lower emissions but high follower costs, while the greedy approach gives lower follower costs, but high emissions. The low value of LM2’s costs in 2b is due to the fact that it does not incur a time-window violation penalty. In the bilevel formulation, the leader is willing to have this violation penalty as long as it results in a lower emissions value.

Figures 3a and 3b respectively show the total emissions and LM follower costs for the three modelling approaches for the “berlin_2_2_2_30” instance. In this instance however, we include a GULP design constraint that all LM DSPs are guaranteed a minimum percentage of the available deliveries. Specifically, $G(\lambda, \mathbf{y}) \geq 0$ takes the form

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}} y_p^d \geq \frac{|\mathcal{P}|}{3} \quad \forall d \in \mathcal{D}. \quad (15)$$

We again see that the bilevel formulation strikes a balance between total emissions and follower costs. In a situation where independent DSPs are

Figure 3: Comparing modelling formulations: “berlin_2_2_2_30” instance with minimum allocation constraint.

required to work together, a collaborative scheme which leads to lower DSP costs may help to incentivize the DSPs to work together.

5.4.2. Optimization methods performance

In the section, we examine the performance of the three following optimization methods to solve the bilevel optimization problem (5): the exact cutting-plane algorithm 1, the surrogate CL model (14) (data-driven approach) and the uncoordinated (greedy) assignment heuristic used by our industrial partner. Figure 4 shows the total emissions (gCO₂eq) for all Berlin instances when comparing the uncoordinated (greedy) approach of our industrial partners with our bilevel approaches. It can be seen that the bilevel approaches produce much fewer total emissions. Averaging over all instances, we see a 31% decrease in emissions when using the cutting-plane algorithm (exact) approach and a 30% decrease in emissions when using the surrogate CL model (data-driven) approach. This shows that incorporating both echelons into the optimization is advantageous compared to an uncoordinated assignment.

Table 3 shows the results for the Berlin instances. The values in bold show the best objective function value obtained across the different modelling approaches. When comparing the exact and data-driven approaches, it can be seen that in several instances, the data-driven approach obtains close or better solutions in a fraction of the time. Looking at the berlin_2_3_2_50 instance for example, it can be seen that the data-driven approach results in lower objective function value in 339.09 seconds, as opposed to the 4523.03 seconds it takes the exact algorithm. For the smaller instances with 10 parcels, the data-driven approach either finds optimal close-optimal solutions. Once the high-cost associated with training the the predictive models

Figure 4: Total emissions (gCO2eq) across all Berlin instances.

has been paid, the data-driven approach is very competitive both in terms of objective function value and solution time. The same pattern can be seen with the Madrid instances in Figure 5 and Table 4. On average, there is a 32% decrease in emissions when using both the cutting-plane algorithm (exact) and the surrogate CL model (data-driven) approaches.

Table 3: Performance of different optimization methods on the Berlin instances of the bilevel 2E problem. Iter. denotes the number of iterations; Time is the runtime in seconds; Obj. is the objective value of the best feasible solution found; Gap is the optimality gap upon termination in percentage.

Method	Cutting-plane algorithm (exact)				Surrogate CL model (data-driven heuristic)		Uncoordinated approach (greedy heuristic)	
	Obj.	Time	Iter.	Gap	Obj.	Time	Obj.	Time
berlin_2_2_2_10	965.61	189.69	4	0.00	967.66	1.86	1413.68	0.18
berlin_2_2_2_30	2271.93	3758.29	4	28.48	2217.46	313.85	3092.48	302.91
berlin_2_2_2_50	3364.29	3925.22	4	47.44	3449.80	342.43	4273.60	304.97
berlin_2_2_3_10	961.26	1594.80	4	0.00	961.26	8.32	1464.92	0.84
berlin_2_2_3_30	2125.77	3617.35	4	25.19	2340.95	774.77	2947.50	302.21
berlin_2_2_3_50	3717.46	4220.37	4	52.71	4042.39	825.55	4011.74	308.28
berlin_2_3_2_10	965.61	269.12	5	0.00	967.66	2.74	2013.37	1.35
berlin_2_3_2_30	2044.27	3614.69	5	22.92	2184.86	317.88	3700.19	602.78
berlin_2_3_2_50	3670.53	4523.03	5	52.50	3580.78	339.09	4382.02	606.68
berlin_2_3_3_10	961.26	3837.95	9	0.00	961.26	31.59	2030.67	1.42
berlin_2_3_3_30	2266.92	3634.18	4	31.96	2334.42	959.89	3482.12	604.12
berlin_2_3_3_50	3561.96	4569.65	4	51.19	3440.46	785.65	4868.21	611.51

Figure 5: Total emissions (gCO2eq) across all Madrid instances.

Table 4: Performance of different optimization methods on the Madrid instances of the bilevel 2E problem. Iter. denotes the number of iterations; Time is the runtime in seconds; Obj. is the objective value of the best feasible solution found; Gap is the optimality gap upon termination in percentage.

Method	Cutting-plane algorithm (exact)				Surrogate CL model (data-driven heuristic)		Uncoordinated approach (greedy heuristic)	
	Obj.	Time	Iter.	Gap	Obj.	Time	Obj.	Time
Instance								
madrid_2_2_2_10	405.97	50.23	3	0.00	405.97	0.48	656.76	0.40
madrid_2_2_2_30	828.88	4225.72	4	37.06	824.11	306.49	1177.42	303.13
madrid_2_2_2_50	1309.35	3916.70	4	51.17	1283.01	348.77	1684.25	304.78
madrid_2_2_3_10	431.24	705.12	5	0.00	438.29	0.64	628.00	0.59
madrid_2_2_3_30	794.48	4279.60	4	40.36	842.87	344.56	1169.94	302.16
madrid_2_2_3_50	1414.53	3936.97	4	58.09	1352.54	507.74	1656.34	309.48
madrid_2_3_2_10	405.97	144.48	4	0.00	460.10	1.34	760.02	1.25
madrid_2_3_2_30	852.85	3617.98	4	40.74	853.64	312.00	1360.28	604.82
madrid_2_3_2_50	1398.35	4283.50	4	56.05	1334.38	391.53	1514.09	613.17
madrid_2_3_3_10	431.24	3796.13	9	0.00	438.29	1.30	968.20	1.56
madrid_2_3_3_30	856.77	2709.28	4	46.41	844.46	472.39	1312.28	605.92
madrid_2_3_3_50	1329.87	4528.09	4	56.04	1224.56	550.30	2030.28	643.99

6. Conclusions

This study investigated a collaborative two-echelon urban logistics problem where multiple delivery service providers (DSPs) are coordinated by a Green Urban Logistics Platform (GULP). We proposed a new game-theoretical formulation for optimizing the operations of the GULP. In this model, both first-mile (FM) and last-mile (LM) DSPs are represented as cost-minimizing stakeholders. The GULP aims to coordinate DSP across the 2E distribution network by assigning parcels to satellite hubs and to LM DSPs. We develop a bilevel optimization formulation where the GULP acts as a leader while DSPs are followers. Follower problems take the form of parameterized vehicle routing problems, i.e. VRPTW for FMs and PDPTW for LMs. We develop exact and data-driven solution methods to solve this single-leader multi-follower game (SLMFG). The exact approach consists of iteratively solving a relaxed single-level problem and adding value function cuts. The data-driven approach uses constraint learning to train emissions models for follower and embed these predictive models within an approximate leader problem. Our numerical experiments illustrate the benefits of the proposed game-theoretical modeling approach to promote greener urban logistics in two-echelon distribution networks. Accounting for DSPs preferences in the model acts as an incentive to encourage stakeholder participation in the GULP. Our findings also reveal that the proposed data-driven optimization method is competitive in finding efficient solutions and significantly reducing computational time. By leveraging the proposed network-oriented learning approach, the surrogate constraint learning (CL) model provides a scalable approach for coordinating DSPs through both echelons of the distribution network.

The key insight of this research lies in the combined optimization of the objectives of both FM and LM while still minimizing overall emissions and respecting the delivery time windows. The separation between the first and last leg of parcel delivery in city centres allows for the use of efficient vehicles but does require that independent service providers agree to entrust the delivery to another player. The proposed Single-Leader Multi-Follower Game (SLMFG) is flexible in the sense that follower problems can be adapted to incorporate additional features such as capacitated vehicles and time-dependent travel times. Future work will explore the incorporation of time synchronization constraints across both echelons. This is expected to yield more complex follower problems and more integrated network-oriented learning approaches.

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Appendix A. Emission factors and energy generation percentages

Table A.5: Emission factor and energy generation percentage used for Berlin instances (International Energy Agency, 2022a; Low-Carbon Power, 2021).

Energy Source	Emission Factor (gCO ₂ eq/kWh)	Generation Percentage (%)
Natural Gas	490	16
Coal	820	25
Hydroelectric Power	24	4
Wind Energy	11.5	43
Solar Energy	48	3
Biomass	230	9

Table A.6: Emission factor and energy generation percentage used for Madrid instances (International Energy Agency, 2022b; Low-Carbon Power, 2021).

Energy Source	Emission Factor (gCO ₂ eq/kWh)	Generation Percentage (%)
Natural Gas	490	17.54
Coal	820	1.45
Nuclear	12	20.34
Hydroelectric Power	24	9.47
Wind Energy	11.5	23.45
Solar Energy	48	15.75
Biomass	230	12

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